

PROSPECTS OF USING SOLAR ENERGY

S. Zoirov¹, J. Patinov², I. Shoqosimov³

Assistant of Samarkand State Pedagogical Institute, Samarkand city, Uzbekistan¹

Samarkand City Technical College No. 6, Samarkand, Uzbekistan²

Student of Samarkand State Pedagogical Institute, Samarkand city, Uzbekistan³

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Abstract. *The advantages and disadvantages of solar energy technologies are both discussed in this article. A number of technical problems affecting renewable energy research are also highlighted, along with beneficial interactions between regulation policy frameworks and their future prospects. In order to help for opening new routes with regard to solar energy research and practices, a future roadmap for the field of solar research is discussed. The development of new solar power technologies is considered to be one of the key solutions for fulfilling a worldwide increasing demand for energy. Prospects for the use of solar panels with semiconductor materials and types of use of solar cell materials are discussed. In our daily life, solar water heating technology has been designed using solar pools.*

Keywords: *solar collectors, alternative energy, renewable resource analysis, solar water heaters.*

Introduction

Today, the increasing demand for energy requires the production of modern, eco-friendly, energy-efficient technologies and to increase the amount of energy per year. It is clear to all of us that our need for electricity on a global scale is increasing day by day. If we consider the last five years, the world's electricity demand is increasing by 50% every year. Despite the development of various technologies of renewable energy sources [1, 2], traditional thermal power plants using coal, oil and natural gas play an important role in large-scale electricity generation [3]. Improving system performance, optimizing operating conditions and system components, heat recovery from waste heat, etc. are some of the methods used to save energy in conventional thermal power plants [4, 5, 28].

This requires the increase and development of alternative energy sources. If we pay attention to the information of the International Energy Agency, if the use of solar energy develops at such a rate, by 2050, 25% of the world's electricity needs will be met by solar energy and reduction of carbon dioxide gas emitted into the environment by 6 billion tons per year is achieved [8, 9, 17]. As we know, solar panels used in the production of electricity are based on semiconductor materials. The sensitivity of these semiconductor materials to light is very high, that is, the electrical conductivity increases up to 1000 times when they were under the effect of light. Silicon is the most common semiconductor material in our world. The technology of obtaining pure silicon and making solar cells from it is cheaper than other semiconductor materials, so it is convenient to make solar panels from silicon cells. Silicon semiconductors can convert 20-25 % of the Sunlight energy into electrical energy [6, 7].

If we pay attention to the developed countries of the world. The German government is expected to increase the use of renewable electricity to 80% by 2030 and 100% by 2035. In 2021,

Uruguay produced 98 percent of all electricity from renewable sources. Denmark gets more than half of its electricity from wind and solar power [23, 24, 25, 26].

Picture 1. Statistics of developed countries using solar energy

The world leader in the production of wind and solar energy. Beijing aims to generate one-third of its energy from renewable sources by 2025. This country is one of the largest investors in renewable energy worldwide [10, 11, 27].

Materials and Methods

Uzbekistan has an average of 300 sunny days a year, which has a potential to produce of 51,000 trillion kWh of energy, or nearly 5,000 times the country's annual energy consumption. By using this potential, Uzbekistan can reduce the need for natural gas, reduce the impact on the environment and improve the standard of living of the population. As a result, 25 percent of the electricity produced in our country is made up of renewable energy sources. This will save about 3 billion cubic meters of natural gas per year. The issue of expanding the use of renewable energy is that today there is an additional demand for 2-3 billion kilowatt hours of electricity in our country, and in the next five years this need is expected to increase to 10 billion kilowatt hours. It means that in order to cover these huge demands the most effective way is to set up solar panels on the roof of houses, schools and other government organizations. With the saved gas, one million households can be supplied with natural gas during the year. The use of non-traditional energy sources creates the basis for using the existing gas, electricity, and coal reserves as little as possible. Therefore, it is a fact that the improvement, development and implementation of energy-saving technologies into the national economy will have a significant impact on the effectiveness of the main sectors of the national economy [14, 15, 16]. Currently, computer modeling of solar energy production projects in all manufacturing plants, educational institutions, and residential homes requires less time for researchers who are conducting research in the use of solar energy and this method costs less than the traditional method [18, 19, 20].

Today, virtual models of the solar collector are being created, and the technologies of effective use of solar energy are being designed and studied in scientific laboratories [12, 13].

Results And Discussion

If we look at the results of the experiment carried out in Samarkand region, the daily electricity consumption of Samarkand region is 15 million 420 kW \pm 10%. 45% of this goes to the consumption of population, 35-40% for production. The consumption for other sectors is 5-10%. Solar water heaters use solar energy to heat water through solar collectors. Flat panel solar collectors which are coated with transparent air-tight casing, absorptive metal plate which is

painted black with water-conducting tubes and insulated on the rear and side walls of the casing to prevent heat loss are widely used.

Figure 2. A device that changes the temperature of water using solar energy. Installation scheme of the test bench of solar collectors. Temperature of solar collectors, reservoir, working environment control system, circulation pumps, anemometer, computer with measurement card module. (https://www.wecf.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/Gender_Sensitive_NAMA-WECF.pdf) [29].

Experimental results show that if concentrators are installed to increase the water temperature through solar collectors, the water temperature will be much higher. In addition, water heaters powered by solar energy can be equipped with concentrators in order to provide sufficient heat for heating water when solar radiation is insufficient. To ensure the full use of solar energy, solar water heater collectors and concentrators should be placed in accordance with the trajectory of the sun's movement. Usually, if the collectors are placed at an angle of 30° to the horizon, the efficiency of using solar energy during the day will be high. Because in this case, the sun's rays fall on the solar collector more during the day. The direction of the solar collector is determined separately, depending on the place of installation, based on preliminary calculations. Usually, the solar collector achieves maximum efficiency when it is installed at an angle to the horizon according to the width of the place where the device is placed.

Table 1. №1 Results of experiment

№	Average temperature of heated water $t, ^{\circ}\text{C}$	Volume of heated water V , liter	To change the temperature of heated water by 37°C conditionally	Environmental indicators and solar radiation			
				Time, c	Intensity of incident radiation W/m^2	Speed of wind-v m/s	Temperature of water $t^{\circ}\text{C}$
1	68	10	27.2	9^{30}	950	0.0	34
2	65	10	25.5	12^{30}	1100	0.5	38
3	55	10	20.0	15^{30}	1050	0.0	39
4	45	10	14.4	18^{30}	820	0.3	38

N-1 experiment. Results of daily measurements of a cone-type household water heater. The experiment was carried out on July 25, 2023 in the city of Samarkand. The sky is cloudless, open air. The temperature of cold water in the system is 19 degrees Celsius.

Table 2. №2 Results of experiment.

№	Average temperature of heated water t, °C	Volume of heated water-V, liter	To change the temperature of heated water by 37°C conditionally	Environmental indicators and solar radiation			
				Time, c	Intensity of incident radiation W/m ²	Speed of wind-v m/s	Temperature of water t°C
1	52	10	18.3	9 ³⁰	760	2.0	19
2	48	10	17.37	12 ³⁰	830	1.0	24
3	42	10	14	15 ³⁰	690	1.5	28
4	38	10	10.53	18 ³⁰	400	1.5	26

N-2 experiment. . Results of daily measurements of a cone-type household water heater. The experiment was carried out on September 5, 2023 in the city of Samarkand. The sky is cloudless, open air. The temperature of the cold water in the system is 18 °C. According to the results we can determine in the Summer we can get hotter water than the Autumn but even in the Autumn the temperature of the heated water is enough to use in a daily life.

Conclusion

In short, if the world's population uses alternative energy sources, it has great potential to provide environmentally friendly, reliable and sustainable energy. Globally, the use of solar energy and wind energy is a promising path that can significantly increase the energy production and reduce energy costs. Using alternative energy sources can reduce the need for fossil fuels, improve people's quality of life, create jobs and contribute to a more sustainable future. We can also implement efficient use of solar energy in our daily life. The use of solar water heater collectors and concentrators in daily life gives high results.

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